

XRaying the city's past

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The proposal seeks to present the experience of PALIMPSEST, a GR-IT Interreg project, where extending the reality of the city is attempted through the insertion of art installations that refer to, document and reconstruct stories and events of the city's past. The project aimed at the creation of an augmented, multi-layered and enriched museum experience in the open urban space, by using digital technologies and co-creation methods. The project is based on the understanding of the city as a palimpsest, where the city's public space is reconstructed by its time layers that are overlaid making visible the vertical time development of the city.

Figure 1 PALIMPSEST's concept diagram

Artists, architects, software engineers, archivists, educators collaborated in a participative and engaging process in order to revive hidden and even lost layers of the city's Immaterial Cultural Heritage and extend the reality of the present by activating its co-existence with the past. PALIMPSEST extends the urban space in a way that digital and physical spheres concur, creating an immersive merge of fiction and reality. There are no fixed roles, as

spectators and protagonists alternate and interchange, blending everyday life with art, thus blurring distinctions and categorisations.

The project was set in three distinct, but interconnected phases. The first phase was about the creation of an archive, with the participation of schools and trans-generational collaboration. Students found stories related to the city's past, from elder people in their familiar environment. Then they transcribed, tagged, and archived them. In the second phase the collected material was uploaded on a digital mobile Application. The users can search for stories using filters; add stories and comments and suggest links among them. They can also use the Booth, an integrated tool in the App, in order to automatically produce animated visualisations of their narrated stories. The App and the Booth constitute tools that help the city's past extend on virtual spheres. In the last phase, PALIMPSEST focused on the creation of art installations in the urban space. Artists selected stories from the archive and then they reinserted them in their original location as art installations. These settings, activated by visitors, are interactive and multi-sensory, with no visible footprint in the urban area.

PALIMPSEST proposes a different museum experience, immersive, personalised, open-air and extended in the city's public space, not in an enclosed building. Exhibits are re-contextualised, re-inserted in their original place, as they are transformed from objects to events, spontaneous and not programmed, creating an evanescent, dreamlike atmosphere. The museum's authority is questioned as it becomes more participatory and the traditional bisection between curators and spectators is defied. The public can post-produce with different media, co-curate and disseminate the content of the museum in a ceaseless creation process of recycling, reusing and remixing cultural assets.

PALIMPSEST extends time through the preservation, merging and co-existence of different time layers; time linearity is abandoned as extension is developed. Consequently, traditional classifications are reconsidered; continuities are restored; interesting assemblages are facilitated; and the complexity of the city's experience, which was sometimes lost, is now restored.

Figure 2 Example of PALIMPSEST's art installations